

INVESTIGATION OF PATTERN STYLE OF WOVEN FABRICS PRODUCED FROM HYBRID WRAP SPUN YARNS ON FABRICATED COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the effect of weave structure on the thermal and mechanical behavior as well as moisture absorption of the PLA/hemp woven fabric composites made by compression molding. The unidirectional woven fabric prepregs were made from PLA (warp) and PLA/hemp wrapped spun hybrid yarn (weft) with two different weave patterns; 8-harness satin and basket. Unidirectional composites with 30 mass% hemp fibre content were fabricated from these prepregs, and compared to wound PLA/hemp hybrid yarn laminates with same composition. The composite made from the satin fabric had significantly lowest porosities and best mechanical properties compared to the composite made from the wound hybrid yarn and basket fabric. The tensile strength and modulus, flexural strength and modulus, and impact strength were 88 MPa, 10.23 GPa, 113.64 MPa, 7.46 GPa, and 24.24 kJ/m², respectively. The effect of weave pattern on water absorption is significant. Although the composite from hybrid yarn laminate has larger water absorption than that of the pure PLA, it exhibits lower moisture absorption than both weaves. Scanning electron microscopy was used to study the micro-structural properties of the composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre Reinforced Plastics (FRP) are increasingly being used in lightweight engineering where performance and energy efficiency play important roles. Along with carbon fibres (CF), glass fibres (GF) and aramid fibres (AR), natural fibres are also used in the production of FRP.

One of the advantages of using thermoplastic composite is its short cycle production process which makes it possible for extensive application in several industries including automobile manufacture, construction of aircraft and ship components and other high volume production. In contrast to a thermosetting composite, it shows better impact strength, easier recyclability and in the case of PLA, even biodegradability. On the other hand, due to the high melt viscosity of the thermoplastic matrix, the fibre impregnation is more complex than for thermosets. Different impregnation methods have been proposed and applied. One promising technique is the fabrication of hybrid yarns being based on the principle of mixing reinforcing fibres and matrix fibres homogeneously during spinning. Hybrid yarns are non-uniform yarns, which contains components with different properties: a reinforcing component and a thermoplastic component [1, 2]. To achieve high mechanical performance of thermoplastic composites the homogeneous fibre/matrix distribution is necessary, which can be achieved with hybrid yarns.

Textile production technology makes it possible to use hybrid yarns as the basis for obtaining an intermediate prepreg, such as in the form of woven, weft knit or warp knit fabrics with the needed properties. With subsequent processing under pressure and at elevated temperature, the melting thermoplastic fibre component is converted to a polymer matrix filling the mould and impregnating the reinforcing fibres. This technology offers new possibilities for a shortened production process for thermoplastic composites and articles made from them [3].

Fabric weaves are using in several applications in fibre reinforced polymers due to their good mechanical properties, such as stiffness, strength and dimensional stability. With the weaving

technology, it is possible to fabricate high density woven structures with load-oriented fibre positioning [4-6].

The strength and stiffness of fabric reinforced composites are influenced by not only the matrix and yarns properties, but also structural parameters of materials such as fabric count and weave pattern. The fabric count determines the number of weft and warp yarns per cm, whereas the weave pattern specifies how the warp and the weft yarns are interlaced. Typical weave patterns are plain, twill, basket and satin [7].

Fabrics which are produced by weaving a large number of thick yarns as warp and a few number of thin yarns as weft are called unidirectional and are used in unidirectional composites. This weave type provides materials with good processability, high stiffness and strength in the warp direction, which is specific for unidirectional composites [8].

In this study, unidirectional hemp-fibre/PLA composites were made by compression moulding from fabrics composed of hybrid yarns [9], and further subjected to different tests in order to investigate the effects of the pattern style of the woven fabrics on the mechanical properties.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The studied composites consisted of a polylactide matrix reinforced with hemp fibres. The components were prepared at a weight ratio of 70/30 (polymer/fibre).

NatureWorks™ PLA Polymer 6202D by the company Cargill Dow LLC (Minnetonka, USA) was used as the matrix material. The used PLA was in filament and fibre form. A 18 tex PLA multifilament yarn and Ingeo™ staple fibre were provided by Trevira GmbH (Hattersheim, Germany). The staple fibres had a fineness of 1.7 dtex and a mean fibre length of 38 mm. Hemp staple fibres (genus species *Cannabis Sativa L*), supplied by Hempage AG (Adelsdorf, Germany), with an average diameter of 20-40 µm and a mean fibre length of 30 mm were used as reinforcement.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Hybrid yarn manufacture

A wrap spinning method was used to make a hybrid yarn structure with the reinforcing hemp fibres straight and parallel to the yarn axis [10]. Within the framework of this study, the hybrid yarn (nominal count of 550 tex) consists of hemp staple fibres used as a reinforcement and PLA staple fibre used as the thermoplastic component. This hybrid yarn was manufactured with wrap spinning technology using a laboratory spinning machine from Mesdan S.p.A. (Brescia - Italy) and a laboratory yarn twist machine from DirecTwist, AGTEKS CO. Ltd. (Istanbul, Turkey). The PLA-hemp fibre weight ratio was 30:70 [9]. The hemp and PLA staple fibres were fed into the carding machine three times in order to parallelize the fibres and achieve good sliver uniformity. Then the sliver was drawn out twice in a roving frame, which blended the fibres and made their orientation more parallel. No twist is added to the sliver during drawing, this is important, as a twist will have a negative influence on composite strength. The obtained drawn out sliver (also named roving) had however poor integrity it was too weak to be able to be collected alone without causing breakage in the roving machine. Therefore, PLA filaments were used as a processing carrier for the PLA/hemp staple fibres in the roving in the final manufacturing step. The roving was further stabilised by using a continuous PLA filament thread, which was wound around the roving strand in the twisting machine. This imparted strength to the strand to prevent it falling apart and gave a better protection for the reinforcing staple fibres during further textile processing, such as weaving [11] or making a prepreg, The hybrid wrap yarn thus consists of two components, one twist-free PLA/hemp staple fibres component in the yarn core, and a filament wound around the core.

2.2.2 UD woven fabrics from hemp/PLA hybrid yarns

In order to manufacture samples of thermoplastic composites, we made woven unidirectional (UD) fabrics from hybrid yarns and PLA filaments on a hand loom weaving machine. The obtained woven fabrics had the PLA/hemp hybrid yarn in the transvers direction of manufacture of the fabric (weft

direction) and were supported by the 18 tex PLA filaments as the warp yarns in the longitudinal direction (8 threads per cm). The fabrics were woven in two different weave patterns; 8-harness satin (4 threads per cm) and basket weave (3 threads per cm). The constructional particulars of fabric used in this study are presented in Table 1. These fabrics have similar characteristics as an unidirectional fabric in the weft direction, as the thin warp yarn reduces the crimp considerably. The woven fabrics obtained can be considered as prepreps for subsequent processing to make composites by compression moulding.

Table 1. Details of constructional particulars of fabrics

Sample	Weave style	Weight (GSM)	Weft yarn	Warp yarn	Wrap count (ends/cm)	Weft count (ends/cm)
1	Satin	344.0	Wrapped spun	18 tex	8	4
	1*8	(22.9)	hemp/PLA hybrid yarn (550 tex)	PLA		
2	Basket	482.0	Wrapped spun	18 tex	8	3
		(48.9)	hemp/PLA hybrid yarn (550 tex)	LA		

2.2.3 Composite manufacturing and testing

Mechanical tests for tensile strength, flexural strength and impact behaviour were conducted on UD composite laminates as a preliminary characterisation of the fabrics made from hemp and PLA in various architecture patterns; satin (8hs) and basket (2/2). Each laminate had 6 layers of 20×20 cm² prepreg to achieve a composite thickness of about 3-4 mm. The laid up prepreps were first put in a vacuum chamber (0.9 mbar; 70 °C) for at least 18 h, to dry before the compression moulding. The UD composite laminates were consolidated at a temperature of 195 °C and a pressure of 1.7 MPa for 15 min in a laboratory hydraulic compression moulding machine from Rondol Technology Ltd. (Staffordshire, UK). These parameters result in optimal impregnation and very low voids in the composite. Neat unreinforced PLA sheets to be used as reference material were made by compression moulding under the same processing conditions of the same PLA fibres and filaments formed to a similar prepreg. Before performing the mechanical testing, the specimens were conditioned for at least 24 hours at 23 °C and 50% relative humidity according to DIN EN ISO 291. The tensile and flexural strength tests on the UD composite sheets were done using an universal H10KT testing machine equipped with a mechanical extensometer (model 100R long travel extensometer) supplied by Tinius Olsen Ltd. (Salford, UK) according to ISO 527 and ISO 14125. The impact test was carried out with the help of a pendulum arm-type impact tester, which works on the principle of the Charpy Impact Test. Standard method of testing was applied as stated in the ISO 179. The specimens used in the mechanical testing were cut from the laminates using laser cutting, and they were tested in the weft direction.

2.2.4 Composite density and porosity

Fibre volume fraction was measured using the density buoyancy method in which the mass of sample (coated with paraffin) is recorded in air and ethanol. Therefore, having obtained composite densities and knowing the densities of the constituent parts i.e. the hemp fibre and PLA resin, the percentage content of the fibres and porosity were calculated [1].

2.2.5 Water absorption test

The effect of water absorption on hemp fibre reinforced composites was calculated using ASTM D570-98. The percentage weight gain of the samples (W_G) was calculated by the weight difference between the sample immersed in distilled water (W_1) and dry sample (W_0), using the equation (1):

$$WG = [(W_1 - W_0) / W_0] \times 100 \% \quad (1)$$

2.2.6 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Fractured surfaces of the composites obtained from the tensile testing were examined using a low-vacuum scanning electron microscopy with a Quanta 200 ESEM FEG instrument from FEI, (Oregon, USA) with an operating voltage of 10-12.5 kV.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Composite porosity

In the current study, composites were produced from satin PLA/hemp hybrid fabrics and basket PLA/hemp hybrid fabrics in a nominal mass ratio of 30 % hemp reinforcement in order to investigate the effect of different weave patterns on the properties of the composites. Unidirectional composites previously made from identical PLA/hemp hybrid yarns, produced by winding the yarn around a metal frame, were used as reference for comparison to the made woven hybrid fabric based composites [9]. Data for composites made from PLA/hemp nonwoven mats from a previous study are also used as reference in this study in order to show the effect of fibre alignment on the porosity content [12]. Table 2 demonstrates the quality of the produced composites from the current study and compared to results from the previous studies [9, 12]. Both the composite density and constituents of the composites were evaluated. From the results, it is possible to conclude that the composite made by unidirectional satin fabric gave significantly lower porosities compared to the winded hybrid yarn laminates, and the value is in the acceptable range [9, 12].

Creation of voids during composite processing is a function of several construction factors including volume fractions of fibres, fibre distribution, fibre diameter and laminate tightness. The porosity content for the composite made from satin fabric (0.96 %) was clearly lower compared to the composite made from basket fabric (4.55 %) and much lower compare to the composite made from a nonwoven mat (16.71 %) [9, 12]. It can probably be attributed to the fact that satin weaves allow individual fibres to be woven in the closest proximity and can therefore produce fabrics with a close ‘tight’ weave compared to basket weave. The tightly woven fabrics are typically the choice to maintaining fibre orientation during the manufacturing process and minimizing resin void size due to the shorter impregnation distance. Therefore, the laminar and crosswise flow of resin along and between the fibres, in between the yarns and fabric layers is easier [13, 14]. Moreover, basket weave has higher quantity of interlace points per unit area compared to satin. Perhaps voids might be present between the interlace points which are higher in basket systems than those of satin [15]. Therefore, the composite made of the satin fabric is of high quality, as shown in Fig. 1 a and b, because of its lower porosity.

3.2 Water absorption characteristics

Fig. 2 shows apparent weight gain (W_G) as a function of time for neat PLA and PLA/hemp reinforced composite samples immersed in water at room temperature (23 °C). All the composites have the same overall fibre weight fraction (30%). As expected the neat PLA shows the lowest water absorption, which is due to the lack of hydrophilic fibres. It is seen that the effect of weave pattern is significant for the composites. Although the composite made from the winded hybrid yarn prepreg has larger moisture absorption than that of the pure PLA, it exhibits lower moisture absorption than both weaves (satin and basket). Actually the matrix pockets and yarn undulation within the weaves provides an easier diffusion path for the moisture to travel within the weave, compared to a composite composed of unidirectional yarns. If the volume of the wavy region is larger, the W_G of a composite would be higher [16, 17]. It is observed that basket weave has higher W_G than satin.

Table 2. Composition of the fabricated composites calculated from the density measurements

Sample	Density (g/cm ³)	Fibre mass fraction (%)	Fibre volume fraction (%)	Matrix volume fraction (%)	Porosity volume fraction (%)
PLA	1.2490 (0.0002)	0.0	0.0	100.0	-
Satin hemp/PLA fabric	1.2978 (0.0032)	30.0	26.31 (0.07)	72.74 (0.18)	0.96 (0.25)
Basket hemp/PLA fabric	1.2508 (0.0090)	30.0	25.35 (0.18)	70.10 (0.51)	4.55 (0.71)
Hemp/PLA yarn laminates	1.2713 (0.0268)	30.0	25.77 (0.54)	71.25 (1.50)	2.97 (2.04)
Hemp/PLA nonwoven	1.0914 (0.0154)	30.0	21.12 (0.31)	61.16 (0.9)	16.71 (1.17)

Note: Data in table are mean (SD).

Fig. 1 SEM images of the fracture surface of the hemp/PLA specimens from: a) satin-weave architecture fabric and b) basket-weave architecture fabric.

Fig. 2. Apparent weight gain against time for the different PLA/hemp composites at room temperature.

3.3 Tensile properties

Table 3 shows the tensile properties of unidirectional (hemp fibres in the longitudinal direction) hemp/PLA composites. It can be seen that the measured values in the case of the wound yarn laminate composite is significantly lower compared to the woven fabric composites. Actually tightly woven fabrics are usually the choice to maintain fibre orientation during the fabrication process, which was not possible in the wound yarn laminate. The tensile modulus and strength of composite for basket 2/2 is lower compared to satin due to its fabric structure, which makes some parts of the composite weaker. The basket weave has a higher crimp compared to the satin weave due to its more interlacement. (See **Error! Reference source not found.**) Less crimp will result in greater strength on the composites as its free inter fibres contribute towards the force. After the weaving process of the fabric, contraction occurs which causes floating of adjacent yarns to join together making a jammed structure whereas the end point of interlacement creates a gap without any reinforcement. This gap will give in the composite a resin rich area, which is the weakest point because of no reinforcement materials. The basket 2/2 weave has more number of interlacings per surface area, which increase the number of stress concentration points and resin rich areas which significantly affect the tensile properties. The jammed fabric structure has influence on the properties of the composites since in this area the resin penetration between the fibres is low. In the case of satin weave each adjacent floating yarn has a different interlacing point which makes it evenly distributed and the even yarns floating distribution with small gap makes it free for the resin to distribute evenly.

The highest strength values (88.06 ± 7.70 MPa) were registered for composites reinforced with hemp/PLA satin fabric, followed by hemp/PLA basket fabric and wound hemp/PLA yarn laminate. As can be seen from the results, the tensile strength and modulus of the PLA were clearly improved by adding hemp fibres, however; the elongation at break was reduced. The reduction in elongation at break in the composites is mainly due to the destruction of the PLA structural integrity by the loading of the natural fibre which leads to faster fracture of the PLA matrix [18].

Table 3. Tensile properties of PLA-based composites

Sample	Tensile strength (MPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Elongation at break (%)
PLA	41.21 (2.25)	2.91 (0.39)	1.92 (0.26)
Satin hemp/PLA fabric	88.06 (7.70)	10.23 (2.67)	1.35 (0.30)
Basket hemp/PLA fabric	81.09 (5.62)	9.20 (1.81)	1.58 (0.22)
Hemp/PLA yarn laminate	72.75 (6.26)	8.77 (1.44)	1.24 (0.36)

Note: Data in table are mean (SD).

3.4 Flexural properties

Fig. 3 shows the flexural strength of hemp/PLA composites. One-Way ANOVA test showed that mean flexural strength and flexural modulus values of materials investigated were significantly different (P -value <0.05). The flexural strength for all composites was significantly higher than for the unreinforced specimens (neat PLA). Flexural modulus was lowest for the neat PLA (4.41 GPa) and highest for the satin composite sample (7.63 GPa), and had the same trend as for the flexural strength.

Different weave pattern has significant influence on the flexural strength of the composites. Satin fabric composite exhibited the highest flexural strength. It is obviously due to the presence of more aligned fibres in the axial direction, which enabled it to hold the flexural stress developed over the surface of the material. Moreover, the satin fabric composite had a less chance for stress concentration due to lower number of interlacing points [19, 20].

Fig. 3. Flexural properties of PLA/hemp composites.

3.5 Impact resistance

Fig. 4 shows the impact energy of hemp/PLA yarn reinforced composites for different laminates. The impact properties of the composites followed the same trend as obtained in the flexural and tensile testing. The impact energy was around 24.2, 23.8 and 16 kJ/m² for satin fabric, basket and winded yarn laminate composite, respectively. It can be seen from the results that the variation in impact strength of the composites was not significantly influenced by the weaving architecture, as the variation is meagre. The higher impact energies for satin and basket laminate compared with winded yarn laminate are mainly because of the presence of a high number of axially oriented fibres since woven fabric composites provide more balanced properties in the fabric plane than unidirectional composites [21].

Fig. 4. Impact strength of the composites relative to their proportion of fibre mass.

3.6 Fractography analysis of damaged specimens

SEM analysis is carried out to investigate the fracture behavior of the composites (Fig. 5 a and b). Figures reveal that the interaction of polymer matrix (PLA) with hemp fibres is strong since the fibre pull-out is too low. Moreover, there is uniform distribution of unidirectional hemp fibres in the PLA matrix.

Fig. 5. SEM images of the fracture surface morphology of composites made of: a) satin-weave architecture fabric and b) basket-weave architecture fabric.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We report the manufacture of hybrid textile yarns containing reinforcing (hemp) and thermoplastic (PLA) components within their structure, the technology for processing them into woven fabrics (prepregs), and the manufacture of thermoplastic composites based on them. We studied the effect of two types of structures for the fabrics, 8-harness satin and basket, on amount of porosity, moisture absorption, mechanical and thermo-mechanical properties. The properties of PLA-based composites were significantly enhanced compared to the pure PLA matrix. The results showed that the unidirectional hemp/PLA composite made by satin-weave architecture fabric possessed the highest tensile, flexural and impact strength compared to the composites manufactured with basket weave architecture fabric and winded hybrid yarn laminate. This improvement in mechanical strength was correlated to that of decrease in void content and fibre misalignments. This means that satin composite is the strongest, stiffest, and toughest. Both satin and basket weaves as reinforcement in the composites are actually more similar to a unidirectional reinforcement, as a very thin PLA weft yarn is used, which reduced the crimp extremely. Tensile, flexural, and impact values of the composites showed the decreasing trend for winded hybrid yarn laminate composites compared to woven fabric composite. However, moisture absorption test did not show a similar trend. Although the composite from the winded hybrid yarn laminate has larger moisture absorption than that of the pure PLA, it exhibits lower moisture absorption than both weaves (satin and basket). The thermo-mechanical tests showed that composites manufactured from satin and basket weave types of composites had lower damping properties compared to yarn laminate which indicates the stress transfer from the hemp fibres to PLA matrix occurs easily without the failure of matrix. Composite from satin and basket weaves had a better storage modulus compared to yarn laminate composite which supported all the results from tensile, flexural, and impact tests.

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